

BIODIVERSITY, EVOLUTION AND BIOSTRATIGRAFIC SIGNIFICANCE OF KONKIAN FORAMINIFERS OF EUXINE-CASPIAN BASIN OF EASTERN PARATETHYS

LAMARA MAISSURADZE¹, KAKHABER KOIAVA²,

LIKA KVALIASHVILI³, SILVIA SPEZZAFERRI⁴

¹Georgian National Museum, Institute of Paleobiology, 0108 Tbilisi, Georgia, lamaramaisuradze@yahoo.com

²I. Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Institute of Geology, 0186 Tbilisi, Georgia, koiava_ka@yahoo.com

³LTD "GeoEngService", 0160 Tbilisi, Georgia, likakvaliashvili@yahoo.com

⁴University of Fribourg, Department of Geosciences, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland, silvia.spezzaferr@unifr.ch

Abstract The Mediterranean and the Paratethys underwent a complex evolution during the Miocene that caused profound geological and environmental changes. They are recorded in the faunal composition of the benthic foraminifera. The evolution and distribution of these organisms from the Eastern Paratethys has been analysed for the Konkian regional stages (Middle Miocene). The biogeographical distribution pattern is used to reconstruct the possible position of marine connections between the Eastern and Central Paratethys and the Mediterranean Sea. Middle Miocene (Konkian) assemblages from the Eastern Paratethys display strong affinity to Mediterranean foraminifera, which suggests that efficient connections between the Eastern Paratethys and the Mediterranean existed during these times. Micropaleontological and geological data collected during the last four decades suggests that Late Badenian deposits in the Central basin can be correlated to the Konkian deposits in the Eastern basin. The transition from the Konkian to the Lower Sarmatian is characterized by a gradual change from rich Konkian stenohaline to poorer Sarmatian euryhaline foraminiferal assemblages. The reasons for this gradual replacement of the population are at present still being debated and it is responsible for the debate about the position of the Konkian/Sarmatian boundary. Some authors place the Middle/Late Miocene boundary contemporaneously with the first occurrence of Sarmatian species whereas others place it at the level where a typical Sarmatian assemblage becomes well established.

Key Words: *Konkian, Foraminifera, Paratethys, Mediterranean.*

Introduction

The Mediterranean and the Paratethys were formed as new marine realms during the Eocene. The alternate opening and closure of efficient marine connections with the Indian Ocean in the East and through the Mediterranean with the North Atlantic in the West led to complex ecological changes. The Paratethys basin disappeared in the Late Miocene (Rögl, 1999). Between the Serravallian and the end of the Tortonian (Pannonian) the Paratethys declined. The sediments

deposited during this interval record the changes in the paleogeography and paleobiogeography previous to the disappearance of the Paratethyan Sea (Steininger & Rögl, 1984; Filipescu, 2004; Erdei et al., 2007; Kováč et al., 2007; Koiava et al., 2012). The partially independent development of the Mediterranean and the Paratethys has led to the establishment and application of separate geochronological time scales. Internal geographical differentiation also took place within the Paratethys with Central and Eastern domains evolving semi-independently (Piller & Harzhauser, 2005).

Despite the new data, which has been produced in the past few years, the bio-geographical evolution of the Paratethys is still poorly understood. Rögl (1999) and successively Popov (Popov et al. 2004) produced a set of paleogeographical maps of the entire Paratethys. However, many questions about the existence and position of marine connections and land bridges are still open.

A summary of several years of investigation by Georgian scientists (Djanelidze, 1961; Djanelidze, 1970; Maissuradze & Koiava, 2005) is here presented. The data includes descriptions of Konkian (Late Badenian, Early Serravallian) foraminifera from various sub-basins of the Paratethys that have never been available before in the western literature. The comparison between Central and Eastern Paratethyan, Black Sea and Mediterranean foraminiferal assemblages contributes towards the clarification of the geological and geographical setting of these basins during the Middle to Late Miocene.

Discussion

At the end of the Karaganian (Late Badenian), a transgressive phase occurred in the Paratethys (Rögl, 1999). The transgression triggered the development of an extended eastern marginal sea (fig. 1) during the Late Badenian, Early Serravallian (Harzhauser & Piller, 2007). According to Rögl (1999) the Paratethys in Konkian times was efficiently connected to the Indo-Pacific in the east while a less efficient connection linked it to the Mediterranean in the west.

A connection between the Eastern Paratethys and the Central Paratethys and a continuous water exchange with the Mediterranean during the Konkian has also been proposed by Kokay (1985), Szczechura (1996), Studencka et al. (1998), Baldi (2006). Harzhauser & Piller (2007) suggested that during the Konkian the previously unstable connections between the Central and Eastern basins became broader.

The locations of the connections between the Eastern Paratethys and the Central Paratethys in the west and the Indian Ocean in the east are as yet uncertain. According to Nevsskaya (Nevsskaya et al., 1986) one connection was in the south or southeastern part of the basin (Eastern Georgia, Trans-Caspian littoral), where the most polyhaline assemblages of molluscs and foraminifers occur (Zhgenti, 1958; 1991; Bidzinashvili, 1967; Djanelidze, 1961; Sudo, 1961). According to Zhizhchenko (1940) and Sudo (1964) the connection has to be placed between the Karadag region in Iran and the Talysh region of northern Iran and southern Azerbaijan. Krashenin-

nikov (Krasheninnikov et al. 2003) suggested, that at the beginning of the Konkian the Eastern Paratethys was connected to the ocean indirectly – stage by stage. In particular they proposed a corridor between Rumania and Bulgaria to connect the Central Paratethys with the Mediterranean and the Atlantic Ocean (fore-Dobruja strait).

Khain (1964) emphasized that the connection between the Eastern Paratethys and the euhaline ocean water was in the western part of the basin, e.g., via the Central Paratethys. According to Didkovski & Nosovskji (1975) this connection was situated along the fore-Dobruja and Birladsky trenches. Goncharova & Ilina (1997) did not exclude the possible existence of a connection between the Eastern and Central Paratethys at the end of the Late Badenian - Konkian.

Micropaleontological and geological data collected during the last four decades suggests that Late Badenian deposits in the Central basin can be correlated to the Konkian deposits in the Eastern basin. The transition from the Konkian to the Lower Sarmatian is characterized by a gradual change from rich Konkian stenohaline to poorer Sarmatian euryhaline foraminiferal assemblages. The reasons for this gradual replacement of the population are at present still being debated and it is responsible for the debate about the position of the Konkian/Sarmatian boundary. Some authors (Kolesnikov, 1940; Ilina et al., 1976) place the Middle/Late Miocene boundary contemporaneously with the first occurrence of Sarmatian species whereas others (Maissuradze, 1971; Muskhelishvili, 1980; Gruzinskaia et al., 1986; Koiava et al., 2008; Maissuradze & Koiava, 2011) place it at the level, where a typical Sarmatian assemblage becomes well established.

This gradual transition is observed in many regions such as: Bursuki in Moldova (Maissuradze, 1980), near the village Galatin in Bulgaria (Kojumdgieva et al., 1978), in the Morilor river-gorge in Romania (Motas et al. 1972) and at the village Ujarma, in the wells Vashliani №1, Karas №1 in eastern Georgia (Maissuradze et al., 2004; Maissuradze & Koiava, 2006; Koiava, 2006; Koiava et al., 2008).

In Transylvania (Roumania) on the boundary between Upper Badenian and Lower Sarmatian the “Tenuitellinata Zone” with planktonic foraminifers was distinguished (Filipesku & Silye, 2008). It should be noted that in the Sartaganian regional substage deposits of Eastern Georgia (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su) by Koiava the species *Tenuitella clemenciae* (Bermúdez) was discovered. The similar foraminifers also were seen by O. Djanelidze (1971) in Sartaganian regional substage deposits of Western Georgia (the gorge r. Dzimiti) and by Krasheninnikov (2003) in Northern Pre-Caucasus (the gorge r. Orlov).

According to their ecological preferences Konkian foraminifera can be subdivided into two groups (fig. 2, 3; Plate 1, 2): stenohaline and euryhaline forms. The first group consists of genera very similar to those observed in modern Mediterranean assemblages. These forms are characterized by stable morphological features and they rarely evolve into endemic species (Maissuradze, 1988).

Benthonic euryhaline genera prevailed in the Sartaganian regional substage, whereas planktonic forms were rare. Lower part of Late Badenian sediments from the Central Paratethys basin are characterized by abundance of polyhaline species similar to species from the correspondent Sartaganian regional substage deposits in the Eastern Paratethys basin (Popescu, 1979). However, Late Badenian assemblages are considerably richer than those from the Sartaganian. The similarity is probably due to the onset of more efficient connections between the two basins, which were both characterized by salinities up to 30-32‰ (Merklin, 1953).

The second group is characterized by poorer and monotonous assemblages mostly consisting of euryhaline species inherited from the previous Sartaganian regional substage and is presented in Veselianskian regional substage of the Eastern Paratethys. These assemblages contain some genera that show a strong tendency to intraspecific variability and often produce endemic species (Maissuradze, 1988). The most representative genera are: *Cycloforina*, *Affinetrina Sinuloculina*, *Spiroloculina*, *Flintina*, *Oolina*, *Discorbis*, *Nonion*, *Porosonion*, *Ammonia*, *Elphidium*, *Bolivina* (fig. 2; fig. 3). This faunal turnover and impoverishment of the assemblage composition during the Veselianskian (including e.g., Crimea, Georgia, Trans-Caucasian and Azerbaijan) may indicate a drastic change of the environmental conditions.

In the Central Paratethys, the upper part of the Late Badenian corresponding to the Veselianskian regional substage is dominated by assemblages, which are rich in euryhaline species and individuals. This dominance is possibly related to a decrease in salinity triggered by the temporary isolation of the basin (Ionesci, 1968; Paghida-Trelea, 1969).

Conclusions

Thus, analysis of the Konkian, foraminifers drives to the following conclusions: the marine genera are more numerous in the Sartaganian and lower part of Upper Badenian, indicating their direct connection with normal salinity sea. Almost all the genera represented in the Sartaganian basin exist in the lower part of Late Badenian as well (Popescu, 1979), but lower part of Late Badenian complex is considerably richer than the Sartaganian. Common genera in terms of species are more diverse in the lower part of Late Badenian. In the Sartaganian euryhaline genera prevail and plankton is rare. Both in the lower part of Late Badenian and Sartaganian endemic species are not observed because in normal salinity basins variability and transformation process is retarded. Common species of common genera for the lower part of Late Badenian and Sartaganian almost do not differ.

The Late Konkian (Veselianskian) and its corresponding upper part of Late Badenian complexes, show that in each of them only most euryhaline genera prevail and only some species of the genera *Porosonion*, *Elphidium* and *Ammonia* are common.

The Konkian and Late Badenian euryhaline foraminifers gave rise to the specific Sarmatian fauna, the majority of which in due course was so transformed that it is difficult to establish their

phylogenetic connections with their ancestors.

Study and analyse of assemblages of Konkian foraminifers in Euxino-Caspian basin approved the already existing biostratigraphic and paleogeographic data suggesting that Konkian deposits of Eastern Paratethys are simultaneous to Late Badenian deposits of Central and Western Paratethys, whereas in Mediterranean region they correspond to Late Serravalian.

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**აღმოსავლეთ პარატეთისის პონტო-კასპიური აუზის
კონკური ფორამინიფერების ბიომრავალფეროვნება,
ეკოლუციური განვითარების კანონზომიერებანი,
ენიშვნელობა ბიოსტრატობრაფიისათვის**

ლამარა მაისურაძე¹, კახაბერ ქოიავა², ლიკა კვალიაშვილი³, სილვია სპეზაფერი⁴

¹საქართველოს ეროვნული მუზეუმი, პალეობიოლოგიის ინსტიტუტი, თბილისი 0108, საქართველო, lamaramaisuradze@yahoo.com

²ი. ჯავახიშვილის თბილისის სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტი, გეოლოგიის ინსტიტუტი, 0186 თბილისი, საქართველო, koiava_ka@yahoo.com

³შპს "გეოინჟინერინგი", 0160 თბილისი, საქართველო, likakvaliashvili@yahoo.com

⁴ფრიბურგის უნივერსიტეტი, გეომეცნიერებათა დეპარტამენტი, 1700 ფრიბურგი, შვეიცარია, silvia.spezzaferri@unifr.ch

რეზიუმე

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ეკოლოგიური ნიშნის მიხედვით კონკური ფორამინიფერები შესაძლებელია დაიყოს ორ – სტენოპალურ და ევრიპალურ ჯგუფებად. პირველი შედგება იმ გვარების წარმო-

მადგენლებისაგან, რომელთა დიდი უმრავლესობა თანამედროვე ხმელთაშუა ზღვის ფორამინიფერების მონათესავეა, შედარებით მყარი მორფოლოგიური ნიშნებით ხასიათდებიან და იშვიათად წარმოქმნიან ენდემურ სახეობებს. მეორე ჯგუფი მცირერიცხოვანია და შედგება იმ გვარებისაგან, რომელთა უმეტესობა ხშირად ენდემურ სახეობებს წარმოქმნიან და ახასიათებთ ინტენსიური შიდასახეობრივი ცვალებადობა. ისინი წარმოადგენენ გვიანკონკური ფორამინიფერების კომპლექსების ძირითად ბირთვის და აგრძელებენ არსებობას სარმატულ აუზშიც. სარმატული საუკუნის დასასრულისათვის კი მორფოლოგიურად იმდენად იცვლებიან, რომ მათ წინაპარ სახეობებთან ფილოგენეტიური კავშირის დადგენა ძნელდება.

პონტო-კასპიური აუზის კონკური ფორამინიფერების კომპლექსების შესწავლამ და მათმა ანალიზმა კიდევ ერთხელ დაადასტურა არსებული ბიოსტრატეგრაფიული და პალეოგეოგრაფიული მონაცემები, რომლის მიხედვითაც აღმოსავლეთ პარატეთისის კონკური ნალექები დასავლეთ და ცენტრალური პარატეთისის გვიანბადენური ნალექების თანადროულია, ხოლო ხმელთაშუაზღვის ოლქში გვიანსერავალურს შეესაბამება.

ILLUSTRATIONS

Fig. 1. European Neogene sedimentary basins and bioprovinces (According to Bolli et al. 1985)

Species	Konkian		Species	Konkian	
	Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
<i>Elphidium angulatum</i> (Egger)			<i>Articulina gibbosula</i> d'Orbigny		
<i>E. jukovi</i> Serova			<i>A. konkensis</i> Bogdanowicz		
<i>E. macellum macellum</i> (Fichtel et Moll)			<i>Bolivina dilatata dilatata</i> Reuss		
<i>E. kudokoense</i> Bogdanowicz			<i>Spirolina austriaca</i> d'Orbigny		
<i>E. antonina</i> (d'Orbigny)			<i>S. ustjurtensis</i> Bogdanowicz		
<i>E. aff. koberi</i> Tollmann			<i>S. konkia</i> Didkowsky		
<i>Nonion tumidulus</i> Pischwanova			<i>Pyrgo inornata</i> (d'Orbigny)		
<i>N. tauricus</i> Krascheninnikov			<i>Nodobacularella sulcata</i> (Reuss)		
<i>Porosonion guriensis</i> O. Djanelidze			<i>N. didkowskii</i> Bogdanowicz		
<i>P. delicatus</i> O. Djanelidze			<i>Peneroplis laevigatus</i> Karrer		
<i>P. martkobi</i> (Bogdanowicz)			<i>Borelis melo</i> (Fichtel et Moll)		
<i>P. granosum</i> (d'Orbigny)			<i>Angulogerina angulosa</i> (Williamson)		
<i>P. subgranosum subgranosum</i> (Egger)			<i>Globulina gibba</i> d'Orbigny		
<i>Affinetrina guriana</i> (O. Djanelidze)			<i>Discorbis kartvelicus</i> Krascheninnikov		
<i>Simuloculina inflata</i> (d'Orbigny)			<i>D. effusus</i> Krascheninnikov		
<i>S. microdon</i> (Reuss)			<i>Melonis pompilioides</i> (d'Orbigny)		
<i>S. pseudoangustissima</i> (Krascheninnikov)			<i>M. pseudosoldanii</i> (Krascheninnikov)		
<i>S. consobrina consobrina</i> (d'Orbigny)			<i>Nonionella karaganica</i> Krascheninnikov		
<i>Cycloforina gracilis</i> (Karrer)			<i>Fursenkoina sreibersiana</i> (Czjzek)		
<i>Varidentela sartaganica</i> (Krascheninnikov)			<i>Bulimina elongata</i> d'Orbigny		
<i>Quinqueloculina akneriana</i> d'Orbigny			<i>B. elongata subulata</i> Cushman&Parker		
<i>Q. akneriana arunica</i> Gerke			<i>Buliminella elegantissima</i> (d'Orbigny)		
<i>Q. angustissima</i> Krascheninnikov			<i>Oolina imeretica</i> (O. Djanelidze)		
<i>Q. ersaconica</i> Krascheninnikov			<i>Reussella spinulosa</i> (Reuss)		
<i>Triloculina intermedia</i> (Karrer)			<i>Uvigerina gracilissima</i> Pobedina		
<i>Spiroloculina aff. kolesnikovi</i> Bogdanowicz			<i>Cassidulina bulbiformis</i> Krascheninnikov		
<i>Hauerina compressa</i> d'Orbigny			<i>C. bulloides</i> Pobedina		
<i>H. thamarae</i> Djanelidze			<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> (Linné)		
<i>H. guriana</i> Djanelidze			<i>Cibicides konkensis</i> Krascheninnikov		
<i>H. tumida</i> Serova			<i>Rotalia maschanliensis</i> Pronina		
<i>H. composita</i> Serova			<i>Elphidiella artifex</i> (Serova)		
<i>H. podolica</i> Serova			<i>Tenuitella clemenciae</i> (Bermúdez)		

Fig. 2. The distribution of Konkian foraminiferas of the Georgia

Species	Geographic Distribution					Species	Geographic Distribution				
	WGEO	EGEO	UKR	MDA	WPC		WGEO	EGEO	UKR	MDA	WPC
<i>Elphidium aculeatum</i> (d'Orbigny)						<i>N. biporus</i> Krasheninnikov					
<i>E. angulatum</i> (d'Orbigny)	•	•				<i>Spirolina austriaca</i> d'Orbigny	•	•	•	•	•
<i>E. joukovi</i> Serova		•	•	•	•	<i>S. konkia</i> Didkovsky		•			
<i>E. koberi</i> Tollmann		•				<i>S. usturtensis</i> Bogdanowicz	•	•			
<i>E. kudokoense</i> Bogdanowicz	•	•				<i>Pyrgo inornata</i> (d'Orbigny)	•			•	
<i>E. macellum</i> (Fichtel and Moll)	•	•	•		•	<i>Nodobaculariella didkovskii</i> Bogdanowicz	•	•	•		
<i>E. antonina</i> (d'Orbigny)	•	•	•		•	<i>N. sulcata</i> (Reuss)	•	•			
<i>Porosonion marikobi</i> (Bogdanowicz)		•				<i>N. konkensis</i> Bogdanowicz	•		•		
<i>P. subgranosum</i> (Egger)	•	•	•		•	<i>Peneroplis laevigatus</i> Karrer	•				
<i>P. guriensis</i> O. Djanelidze	•	•				<i>Borelis melo</i> (Fichtel and Moll)	•	•	•	•	•
<i>P. delicatus</i> O. Djanelidze	•	•				<i>B. haueri</i> (d'Orbigny)			•		
<i>P. granosum</i> (d'Orbigny)	•	•				<i>Globulina gibba</i> d'Orbigny		•	•		
<i>Affinetrina guriana</i> (O. Djanelidze)	•	•				<i>Discorbis kartvelicus</i> Krasheninnikov	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Simuloculina consobrina consobrina</i> (d'Orbigny)			•			<i>D. effusus</i> Krasheninnikov	•				•
<i>S. consobrina sarmatica</i> (Gerke)			•		•	<i>D. risillus</i> Bodanowicz			•		
<i>S. microdon</i> (Reuss)	•				•	<i>D. ukrainicus</i> Satanovskaya			•		
<i>S. inflata</i> (d'Orbigny)	•					<i>Melonis pompilioides</i> (d'Orbigny)		•	•	•	•
<i>S. pseudoangustissima</i> (Krascheninnikov)	•				•	<i>M. pseudosoldanii</i> (Krascheninnikov)	•	•			•
<i>Cycloforina gracilis</i> (Karrer)	•	•	•		•	<i>Nonionella karaganica</i> Krascheninnikov	•				
<i>V. sartaganica</i> (Krascheninnikov)	•	•			•	<i>Fursenkoia sreibersiana</i> (Czjzek)	•				
<i>Quinqueloculina intermedia</i> (Karrer)	•					<i>Bulimina elongata</i> (d'Orbigny)	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Q. akneriana</i> d'Orbigny	•	•			•	<i>B. elongata subulata</i> Cushman and Parker	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Q. ersaconica</i> Krascheninnikov	•	•				<i>Buliminella elegantissima</i> (d'Orbigny)	•				•
<i>Q. akneriana arunica</i> Gerke	•					<i>Oolina imeretica</i> (O. Djanelidze)	•				
<i>Q. angustissima</i> Krascheninnikov	•				•	<i>Reussella spinulosa</i> (Reuss)	•				•
<i>Triloculina inflata</i> d'Orbigny	•					<i>Uvigerina gracilissima</i> Pobedina	•	•			•
<i>T. intermedia</i> (Karrer)	•					<i>Cassidulina bulbiformis</i> Krasheninnikov	•	•			•
<i>Spiroloculina aff. kolesnikovi</i> Bogdanowicz	•					<i>C. bulloides</i> Pobedina	•				
<i>Articulina konkensis</i> Bogdanowicz	•		•	•	•	<i>Ammonia beccarii</i> (Linné)		•			•
<i>A. gibbosula</i> d'Orbigny	•	•	•	•		<i>A. aff. viennensis</i> d'Orbigny			•		•
<i>A. tenella</i> (Eichwald)	•					<i>Cibicides konkensis</i> Krasheninnikov	•				
<i>Bolivina dilatata</i> Reuss	•	•			•	<i>Rotalia maschanliensis</i> Pronina	•	•	•	•	•
<i>Hauerina composita</i> Serova	•	•				<i>Elphidiella artifex</i> (Serova)		•			
<i>H. guriana</i> O. Djanelidze	•					<i>Angulogerina angulosa</i> (Williamson)	•	•			
<i>H. lamarae</i> O. Djanelidze	•					<i>Canalifera eichwaldi</i> (Bogdanowicz)					•
<i>H. podolica</i> Serova	•				•	<i>Lenticulina inornata</i> (d'Orbigny)					•
<i>H. thamarae</i> O. Djanelidze	•	•				<i>L. simplex</i> (d'Orbigny)					•
<i>H. tumida</i> Serova	•					<i>Dendritina elegans</i> d'Orbigny			•		
<i>Nonion bogdanowiczi</i> Voloshinova			•			<i>Florilus boueanus</i> (d'Orbigny)			•		•

WGEO - Wester Georgia; EGEO - Eastern Georgia; UKR - Ukraine; MDA - Moldova; WPC - Western Precaucasus.

Fig. 3. The distribution of foraminifera in the Konkian deposits at the various regions of Eastern Paratethian

Plate 1. Konkian Foraminifera: 1. *Elphidium* aff. *negranicus* Voloshinova, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 2. *Elphidium* aff. *alizadei* Voloshinova, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 3. *Elphidium gombori* sp.n., (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 4. *Nonion tumidulus* Pishvanova, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 5. *Nonion* aff. *umbostelligerum* Serova, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 6. *Nonion* aff. *tauricus* Krasheninnikov, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 7a, b. *Elphidium horidum* Bogdanowicz, (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 8a, b. *Elphidiella* aff. *artifex* (Serova), (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 9. *Porosonion granosum* (d'Orbigny), (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 10. *Porosonion guriensis* (O. Djanelidze), (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 11. *Porosonion martkobi* (Bogdanowicz), (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 12. *Uvigerina gracillissima* Pobedina, (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 13a, b. *Sinuloculina consobrina* (d'Orbigny), (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 14. *Sinuloculina consobrina* (d'Orbigny), (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 15. *Quinqueloculina hauerina* d'Orbigny, (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su).

Plate 2. Konkian Foraminifera: 1a, b. *Tenuitella clemenciae* (Bermúdez), (the gorge r. Arkhashen-su); 2a, b. *Tenuitella* aff. *clemenciae* (Bermúdez), (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 3a, b. *Ammonia* aff. *vienensis* (d'Orbigny), (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 4. *Ammonia* sp., (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 5a, b. *Ammonia beccarii* (Linné), (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 6. *Quinqueloculina akneriana argunica* Gerke, (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 7. *Borelis melo* (Fichtel & Moll), (the road Tbilisi-Gombori near the village Ujarma); 8. *Spiroloculina* sp., (the gorge r. Dzimiti); 9. *Articulina* aff. *gibbosula* (d'Orbigny), (the gorge r. Dzimiti).